

IMPROVING THE INTELLECTUAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Jalilova Iroda Alisher's daughter

ICT specialist, Department of Preschool Education,
Khojaabad District, Andijan Region

Abstract: In this article, detailed information was given about the work carried out in the higher education institution to develop scientific and research work at a high level, to ensure the development of senior specialists by improving the qualifications of university graduates.

Keywords: Innovation, university, research, technology, professionalism, experience, practice, degree, research..

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The order on the approval of the rules for determining the teaching load of the teaching staff of the higher education institution and the teaching-methodical, scientific-research and "master-student" work was registered with the Ministry of Justice. With this document, the teaching load of the teaching staff of the Higher Education Institution and the rules for determining the teaching-methodical, scientific-research and "master-apprentice" work were approved. It was recommended that the amount of teaching (lecture, practical (individual), seminar and laboratory) hours of professors should not be less than 400 hours.

For the first time in Uzbekistan, we reported on the ranking of higher education institutions. According to the author of the rating - the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers, the inspectorate is currently developing a separate web portal for the national rating system of educational institutions. In the near future, complete information on the rating of higher education institutions will be publicly announced. The official website of the inspectorate also provided a number of infographics on the activities of higher education institutions of Uzbekistan.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further strengthen the infrastructure of scientific research institutions and develop innovative activities" No. PQ-3365 of November 1, 2017, "Improving the mechanisms for introducing innovations into economic sectors on additional measures" No. PQ-3698 of May 7, 2018 and "Measures to further reduce bureaucratic barriers and introduce modern management principles into the

activities of state bodies and organizations on" in accordance with decisions No. PQ-4546 dated December 9, 2019, as well as in order to improve the normative legal framework for the formation and implementation of the state order for scientific and research works, the Cabinet of Ministers decides:

1. The following:

In accordance with Annex 1 of the regulation on the state order for scientific research works;

In accordance with Appendix 2 of the Regulation on the procedure for selecting and financing "Startup" projects;

The regulation on scientific and technical councils under the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan should be approved in accordance with Appendix 3.

2. Let the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with other interested ministries and agencies, harmonize the normative legal documents they have adopted with this decision within one month.

3. The Minister of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.Y. will supervise the implementation of this decision. Abdurahmanov and the Secretariat of the Cabinet of Ministers for the development of telecommunications, IT-technologies and innovative activities, ensuring information security.

During 2018-2019, 24 higher education institutions (HEIs) were involved in attestation by the Education Inspectorate, 10 of them (41.7%) were recognized as "Passed the Attestation" and accredited. 13 of them (54.2%) were recognized as "conditionally passed the certification" and they were given 1 year to eliminate the shortcomings. 1 HEI (4.2%) was recognized as "Did not pass certification" and was not accredited.

If you notice, only 42% of HEIs are certified, and the remaining 54% are conditionally certified, which means they are given another chance. But unfortunately, many HEIs did not use this opportunity effectively.

In September of this year, the State Inspection carried out re-attestation of uncertified educational areas, master's specialties and specializations of 22 HEIs and 5 scientific research institutions.

According to the re-attestation result:

17 out of 40 educational fields (42.5%) "Did not pass certification" (TAQI - 1, TDMRXOM - 1, TATU - 2, UzDK - 3, TKTI - 1, TDTU - 2, TerDU - 2, GulDU - 1, JizDPI - 3, TDAU Nukus f. - 1);

4 out of 17 master's specialties (23.5%) "did not pass certification" (TDTU - 4);

19 out of 60 specialties (31.7%) "Did not pass the certification" (BuxDU-1, BuxDTI-1, TDAU-2, TDTU-9, TIQXMMI-1, Tashkent Institute of Advanced

Training of Doctors-4, Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry- 1) was concluded and the reception was stopped.

The main reasons for failure to re-certify educational fields, specializations and specializations:

In 20% of HEIs, it was found that the causes of deficiencies identified during the initial certification process were not systematically studied, that the management of HEIs and officials did not draw appropriate conclusions, that the issue was approached irresponsibly, that systematic control was not established, and that the "roadmaps" adopted for the elimination of these problems were not monitored. In particular, TAQI, TATU, TerDU, TAYLQEI, TKTI, O'DSMI have not eliminated objections to the previous attestation;

In 35% of higher education institutions, the level of students' mastery of science programs is still low due to the low quality of lessons taught by professors and teachers, insufficient imparting of modern knowledge, their lack of regular work on themselves and lack of attention to independent education (TDTU - 5, TerDU - 1, TATU - 1 TKTI - 1, AndMI-1, GulDU - 1, JizPI - 2) were observed.

So, education is an activity aimed at independent acquisition of knowledge is an integral part of the process. At the initial stage of studies in HEIs organization of independent work is related to a number of tasks in this process Each professor-teacher initially depends on the student's abilities and mental capabilities instill confidence, guide them with patience and step by step independent education correctly proves the need to teach organization.

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